

Generative Flow-Matching Modeling of the Neurodevelopmental Connectome via Dynamic Hypergraphs

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Abstract

Human brain structure datasets are regularly small and lack a representative sample of target phenotypes. Augmenting these is often challenging due to highly complex patterns of connectivity, and this issue is particularly emphasized when there are significant target class imbalances. We introduce a model that enables the generation of novel data instances and data exploration. Specifically, we consider the case of preterm birth, where datasets include very few preterm individuals. We present a diffusion-style flow-matching framework, whereby conditioning on continuous gestational age (GA), the model learns the underlying geometry of the brain and can reproduce differences in connectivities for infants born at varying numbers of weeks. This approach is inspired by the brain's fundamental capacity for self-organization. Moreover, to understand the real implications of varying GA on the organization of the developing brain, we integrate a dynamic

hypergraph layer. This allows the model to dynamically learn the higher-order dependencies that evolve in the brain, facilitating the generation of biologically plausible structural topologies. To ensure appropriateness and sufficiency in the generated networks, we utilize biologically informed losses. Additionally, we compare the generation with key graph metrics commonly employed in neurobiological studies of brain structure. Our model results demonstrate biologically realistic connectivity patterns discovered through the dynamic hypergraph approach. The code is publicly available at: <https://github.com/Katherine-Birch/Generative-Flow-Matching-Modeling-of-the-Neurodevelopmental-Connectome-via-Dynamic-Hypergraphs>

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Biological networks**; *Health informatics*; • **Mathematics of computing** → **Hypergraphs**; *Markov processes*; • **Computing methodologies** → *Learning latent representations*; **Neural networks**.

Keywords

Generative AI, Neuroscience, Hypergraph, Flow matching, Preterm birth

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ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-2259-2/2026/08

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3770855.3819022>

ACM Reference Format:

Katherine Birch, Alberto Durán-López, Daniel Bolaños-Martinez, Maria Bermudez-Edo, Roman Bauer, and Suparna De. 2026. Generative Flow-Matching Modeling of the Neurodevelopmental Connectome via Dynamic Hypergraphs. In *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining V.2 (KDD 2026)*, August 9–13, 2026, Jeju Island, Republic of Korea. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 11 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3770855.3819022>

1 Introduction

The human brain undergoes an intensive period of non-linear development during the final stages of pregnancy. This phase is characterized by rapid reinforcement of brain structures, such as small-world architecture [16, 32] and the emergence of structural hubs and global communication [1, 2, 16, 33]. For infants born prematurely, this developmental trajectory is disrupted. Understanding the divergences between preterm and term born infants at birth can give important insights into group-level differences in structures as they emerge [1, 4, 19, 25, 28]. However, acquiring the data required for these analyses is challenging. The field suffers from small datasets, with low numbers of target phenotypes. This is particularly pronounced when considering infant development due to the high cost of MRI and the difficulty in imaging such small infants [33]. This creates a challenge whereby standard models struggle to distinguish between classes, being prone to overfitting and majority class collapse [4, 6, 22]. To overcome these issues, we propose a generative method designed to implicitly learn biological structures from sparse data. Adapting principles from architectures that capture long-range dependencies in networks [7], our framework considers the connectome as a unified topology instead of isolated pairwise connections. By implicitly deriving the brain’s latent spatial topography, we model structural variation across continuous gestational ages.

We introduce a model that allows generation of novel cases of data, at different gestational ages (GA). We move away from explicitly programmed targets and structural information, through the use of dynamic hyperedge membership, and Conditional Flow Matching. In summary, we introduce three key contributions:

- (1) We introduce a generative framework capable of interpolating novel data instances across the entire gestational age (GA) window. By conceptualizing neurodevelopment as a continuous trajectory rather than a series of discrete temporal snapshots, the model enables the high-fidelity simulation and exploration of the diverging structural connectomes of preterm and term-born infants.
- (2) We demonstrate that the model can produce both biologically plausible and mathematically sufficient connectivity. Using a selection of neurobiological metrics, we provide a validation framework for our synthetic data samples.
- (3) Our model proposes a novel integration of Dynamic Hypergraph, with Constrained Flow Matching. By employing a composite, biologically informed loss function the model implicitly learns higher-order structures and maturation trends.

2 Related work

Traditional methods of generating brain connectivity graphs used stochastic models guided by explicit, biologically inspired rules [3].

While useful for testing assumptions surrounding the mechanism by which brains self-organise, they lack implicit awareness of gestational age (GA). This means that while they can often reproduce global structures expected from brain graphs, they generate average cases. More recent work by Liu et al. [21] applied a conditional Variational Autoencoder (CVAE) to model adult brain connectivity optimized for Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence and reconstruction losses. They successfully reproduce structural connectivity patterns from individual subjects, conditioned on lifestyle and cognitive factors. While this provides a good baseline for generation, the model is reconstructive, learning a mapping for specific individuals within the dataset. This means that the model does not learn to generate novel cases and is prone to struggle on minority classes. Furthermore, to overcome data sparsity, they rely on mean imputation for missing GA cases, which may cause oversmoothing of neurodevelopmental trajectories and disruptions. Other recent work [38] have focused on continuous modeling of the developing brain through diffusion based models. Xie et al. [38] introduce a graph-diffusion model that is able to produce realistic simulations of the maturing surface of the brain. Their model is able to rely on standard diffusion models, where iterative denoising steps are able to capture small nuances in surface texture of the brains. Their methodology focuses on high-resolution data, while our problem relies on small datasets, of high-order global structural connectivity. Therefore, we require a model which can ensure stability, while taking advantage of the continuous modeling of gestation from Xie et al. [38].

To overcome some difficulties faced by traditional diffusion models, Flow Matching has emerged as an alternative. Flow Matching is a deterministic generalization of diffusion, reducing computational cost by learning a straight line path between noise and target [20, 39]. Zhang et al. [42] use flow models in the social science domain, where specific connectivity patterns are expected based on prior knowledge. They reward the model based on its ability to achieve certain structural objectives as well as raw data distribution. However, by conditioning on target connectivity patterns, the model cannot implicitly learn how those patterns arise.

To improve biological realism, Zuo et al. [43] used a VAE-GAN architecture to inform the model of structural information regarding which side of the brain each node belongs to. By introducing biological priors, they demonstrate an improvement in Alzheimer’s classification on an adult dataset. While this represents a step in biologically aware models, the modeling of hemisphere separation introduces explicit information about expected connectivity patterns. We can adapt these structural priors to become implicitly aware of developing connectivity structures.

Moreover, most models rely on pairwise regional interactions within the brain [43]. Early statistical models used graph metrics to explore how the brain balances global integration with local communication [32]. Another study showing that the brain is better characterized by higher-order interactions between regions is Xiao et al. [37]. In their paper, they learn a hypergraph representation of the connectivity matrices to discover higher-order interactions. Other researchers have also used hypergraph structures for exploring brain functional connectivity [9, 10, 27, 41]. Functional data generally differs from structural brain connectomes, as it often includes more ROIs and temporal changes within an individual. Yuan et al. [41] applied hypergraph representations to structural

and functional connectomes by integrating hyperedge relationships into a contrastive learning mode. While this is a strong model for identifying differences, it lacks the ability to generate novel data cases or to simulate continuous maturation.

The central challenge in generative modeling of brain development is the inability to simulate continuous, higher-order maturation while maintaining individual differences. Existing models suffer from combinations of “age-blindness”, explicit biological constraints tending models toward prescriptiveness, and difficulty in balancing local and global integration. Therefore, a model that implicitly learns the continuous development of brain structure, while discovering and reproducing complex structures, is highly needed.

3 Method

3.1 Dataset

We use data from the developing human connectome project (dHCP) which is a large-scale study into the human brain at the time of birth, [12] processed by [33] and available on their GitHub. This includes diffusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging (dMRI) data from 520 newborn infants. Data was collected at term-normalized age, meaning that all infants were imaged shortly after their “due date”. The age indicated is gestational age (GA), which is the number of weeks from conception to the date of birth.

The brain structural connectome for each infant is encoded as a symmetric adjacency matrix $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, where N is the number of nodes, representing distinct regions. The entry $A_i[u, v]$ gives the strength of the connection between region u and region v .

3.2 Input Encodings

3.2.1 Node Features. We initialize the node representations with a base embedding $e_i^{(0)}$ which combines anatomical information about the corresponding brain region. This base node embedding is:

$$e_i^{(0)} = \text{Emb}_{reg}(r_i) + \text{Emb}_{lobe}(l_i) + \text{Emb}_{surf}(s_i) + \text{Emb}_{hemi}(h_i) + \text{MLP}_{coord}(x_i, y_i, z_i), \quad (1)$$

where r_i, l_i, s_i and h_i are the region, lobe, surface, and hemispheres for each index, as defined by the brain parcellation atlas [33]. Coordinates represent the centroid of each brain region in the infant brain atlas that was used in the initial processing of the dMRI data [29, 30].

While there is spatial information in these features, connectivity patterns arise from the relative dependencies between nodes. Therefore, we add a multihop transformer layer, to attend to these embeddings in relation to each other. We fuse the information from the hypergraph and the transformer, to synthesize local and global topologies into a unified representation.

3.2.2 Edge Features. In the dataset, edges refer to physical connections between regions in the brain. Therefore, we treat edges as carriers that allow for information flow throughout the network. We include them in hyperedges alongside nodes to facilitate interaction between and within hyperedges. We distinguish two conditions for edges in the hypergraph:

- **Reinforcement:** These are edges that connect two nodes within the same hyperedge. The strength of the edge reinforces the structural cluster of the hyperedge.

- **Bridges:** These are edges that connect nodes in distinct hyperedges. We calculate the signal of these to inform the proximity between the latent clusters. This allows the model to understand the global relationship between the hyperedges.

3.3 Structural reasoning streams

3.3.1 Multihop transformer. While the node features contain anatomical and spatial information, connectivity patterns inherently depend on the relative topology between regions. To capture this relational persistence, we pass the initial node embeddings through a Multihop Transformer layer. To ensure the transformer reacts to the temporal flow process, the anatomical node embeddings are dynamically updated at each timestep. The node strengths are calculated and injected into the node representations. The embeddings are processed via a Multi-Head Self-Attention mechanism. To ensure the representation remains grounded in the physical brain network, the attention matrix is constrained by an adjacency mask, allowing regions to attend exclusively to their M -hop topological neighbors. Based on initial empirical evaluations demonstrating a negligible topological impact beyond a two-hop radius, we restrict this attention mechanism to $M = 2$ layers to avoid over-smoothing. By stacking these attention layers (e.g., $M = 2$ hops), the transformer generates dynamically shifted, locally-integrated node embeddings. These localized representations are subsequently fused with the global communities discovered by the hypergraph.

3.3.2 Hypergraph formation. Features from nodes are passed to the dynamic hypergraph layer to explore communities within the brain structure. The model generates a membership matrix H which allows grouping of nodes. We use a soft-assignment which allows for nodes to participate in multiple hyperedges, and this membership is recalculated at every graph state x_t . This allows the model to learn different patterns of connectivity as the state evolves. In order to facilitate the dynamic membership of nodes within hyperedges, we implement entropy loss with a dual-objective. We aim to balance the “sharpness” of communities, with the “diversity”. This means that while we use a soft-assignment, we incentivize the model to decisively group nodes into hyperedges. However, we also push the model to prioritize diverse hyperedges across the full feature space instead of a few large, non-specific groups. Importantly, these hyperedges represent latent clusters not simply anatomical groupings, and which evolve with the graph state.

3.3.3 Soft assignment. We model the hypergraph as a probabilistic soft assignment, allowing nodes to belong to multiple latent clusters rather than enforcing rigid anatomical boundaries. We define a learnable incidence matrix $H \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times K}$, where K is the total number of latent hyperedges, and each entry $h_{ik} \in [0, 1]$ represents the membership strength of node i in hyperedge k . We parameterize H as a learned function of the anatomical node embeddings $E^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$. H is computed by projecting $E^{(0)}$ into latent space and applying a sigmoid activation:

$$H = \sigma \left((E^{(0)} \cdot W_{proj}) \cdot W_h \right), \quad (2)$$

where $W_{proj} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_{lat}}$ is a learnable projection matrix that transforms node features into a latent space, and $W_h \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{lat} \times K}$ is the

Figure 1: Overview of proposed Generative Flow Matching training pipeline. The model consists of a standard flow-matching MLP backbone, conditioned with gestational age (GA). Structural information about the brain geometry is fed to parallel Dynamic Hypergraph, and Multihop Transformer streams which are fused in order to learn complex topological structures. These three components are combined to predict the total velocity (v_θ) which is used to define a probability path between the noise distribution and the target brains through iterative ODE solving.

hypergraph weight matrix that assigns the nodes to latent hyperedges.

3.3.4 Dual-objective entropy loss for hyperedge membership. We combine the sharpness loss (binary entropy loss) with the diversity loss (Shannon entropy loss) to encourage the model to learn distinct and decisive communities. The binary entropy loss is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{sharp} = -\frac{1}{N \cdot K} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \left(h_{ik} \ln(h_{ik}) + (1 - h_{ik}) \ln(1 - h_{ik}) \right). \quad (3)$$

The diversity loss is calculated as:

$$p_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N h_{ik}}{\sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^N h_{ij}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{div} = -\frac{1}{\ln(K)} \sum_{k=1}^K p_k \ln(p_k). \quad (5)$$

Overall, the total loss for the hypergraph membership is a weighted sum of these two components:

$$\mathcal{L}_{entropy} = \beta_1 \mathcal{L}_{sharp} - \beta_2 \mathcal{L}_{div}. \quad (6)$$

3.3.5 Normalization constraints on membership. To aggregate features within a hyperedge, while preventing signal explosion in large communities, we introduce a parameterized normalization constraint. The aggregated hyperedge feature E_k is computed as:

$$E_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N h_{ik} \cdot z_i}{(d_k)^\alpha}, \quad (7)$$

Where z_i is the projected node features, d_k is the degree of hyperedge k , and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is a learnable parameter constrained by

Sigmoid activation. This allows the model to learn the optimal balance between reinforcing the community structure (sum-pooling, $\alpha > 0$), and maintaining a stable signal (mean-pooling, $\alpha > 1$) across the graph.

3.3.6 Dynamic edge context. At each iteration, the noisy graph state x_t is fed into the hypergraph layer, which allows the model to learn how the hyperedge memberships evolve as the graph state changes. This allows the model to learn how different patterns of connectivity emerge across the maturation process. The dynamic hypergraph layer is designed to capture both local and global topological features, by allowing nodes to belong to multiple hyperedges and by learning the relationships between these hyperedges through the bridge edges. Consequently, the communities dynamically update their latent representations at every timestep based on the evolving connectivity.

When hyperedges are updated with both node and edge signals, this is propagated back to the nodes. The updated node features, \tilde{z}_i , are computed by projecting hyperedge features E_k back to the membership matrix H , using the same α -constraint as the aggregation step:

$$\tilde{z}_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K h_{ik} \cdot E_k}{(d_i)^\alpha}, \quad (8)$$

where $d_i = \sum_{k=1}^K h_{ik}$ is the soft degree of node i . The model functions as a dual-stream conditioning system. The hypergraph learns the global communities, while the multihop transformer learns the local relationships between nodes. These streams are combined via layer normalization to synthesize local and global topologies. These combined representations are processed independently from

the core flow-matching MLP. The structural reasoning streams project the unified representation into a structural embedding space, which is then added to the backbone MLP output, as a graph-aware inductive bias.

3.4 Generative model

3.4.1 Flow-matching. We employ Conditional Flow Matching (CFM) [20] to implicitly learn the mapping between Gaussian noise and the complex brain connectivity. This draws a linear probability path between the real data (x_0) and the noise distribution (x_1):

$$x_t = (1 - t)x_0 + tx_1, \quad t \in [0, 1]. \quad (9)$$

From this path, the CFM learns a vector field (v_θ), which is the derivative of the path with regards to t . This v_θ is optimised using Huber loss, due to the heavy-tailed distributions of the brain connectivity matrices. Overall, CFM is shown to provide stability during training, while allowing the dynamic hypergraph to explore the higher-order structure of the brain matrices. At inference we predict the novel brain graphs at a certain condition value (c) by solving the system of first-order ODEs :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = v_\theta(x_t, t, c), \quad (10)$$

from $t = 1$ to $t = 0$, and where c is gestational age (GA). We update the graph state, x_t , through the Euler method:

$$x_{t-dt} = x_t - v_\theta(x_t, t, c) \cdot dt. \quad (11)$$

By conditioning on GA, we are able to specify the target age, to generate age appropriate networks. In Figure 2 we demonstrate the differing trajectories, starting from identical Gaussian noise. In order to improve robustness of this learning, and encourage the model to learn the relative effect of biological maturity on structure, we use classifier-free guidance. This allows the model to learn both the conditioned (v_c) and unconditioned (v_u) structures simultaneously.

3.4.2 Biologically informed losses. The brain connectivity matrices show heavy-tailed distributions, where there are a small number of high-strength ‘‘hubs’’ and many weaker nodes and connections. These hubs are particularly important as a feature of the development. In order to ensure that this is not diluted, we apply Huber loss. This retains nuance required for the biological data, by applying quadratic MSE for small error values, and MAE linearity at higher values.

3.5 Evaluation metrics

To assess the topological fidelity and biological plausibility of the generated networks, we evaluate based on graph-theoretical metrics. This allows us to observe how well the model has reproduced complex network characteristics.

We split these into two categories to clearly demonstrate the scale that they are working on [26]:

3.5.1 Global performance metrics. In this category we calculate the Global Efficiency, the Spectral Wasserstein Distance and the Value Wasserstein Distance of the network. These assess the overall

alignment of the synthetic data with the real test set. Results are reported in Table 2

- *Global efficiency*(ϵ): This gives a measure of how efficiently the network allows information exchange:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i \neq j \in G} \frac{1}{L_{ij}}, \quad (12)$$

where N : The total number of nodes in the graph. L_{ij} : The shortest path length between node i and node j [18].

- *Spectral Wasserstein Distance* (W_{spec}): Gives a distance between the eigenvalue distributions of the graph Laplacians ($L = D - A$):

$$W_{spec} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\lambda_i^R - \lambda_i^S|, \quad (13)$$

where the sorted eigenvalues of real and synthetic Laplacian matrices are given by λ^R and λ^S .

- *Value Wasserstein Distance* (W_{val}): This gives the distance between the two cumulative distribution functions of edge weights for real and synthetic data (F_P and F_Q):

$$W_{val}(P, Q) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |F_P(x) - F_Q(x)| dx, \quad (14)$$

3.5.2 Topological fidelity. These look more closely for specific patterns of connectivity that are commonly found in the human brain structural connectome [32]. We focus on characteristics that demonstrate the diverse range of biological connection patterns. Results are reported in Table 3

- *Clustering Coefficient* (C): This indicates how densely connected neighbours are by observing how many triangles form within the network [36]:

$$C = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{v \in G} c_v, \quad (15)$$

where c_v is the clustering coefficient for node v .

- *Small-World Index* (ω): This metric measures the tendency for all nodes to be connected to one another through a short number of ‘‘hops’’ [13]. This is a ratio of how clustered the network is, against how integrated the network is:

$$\omega = \frac{C/C_{rand}}{L/L_{rand}}, \quad (16)$$

where C_{rand} and L_{rand} come from approximations of Erdős-Rényi graphs. These were:

$$C_{rand} \approx p_{er} = \frac{|\mathcal{E}|}{N(N-1)/2}, \quad (17)$$

and

$$L_{rand} \approx \frac{\ln(N)}{\ln(\langle deg \rangle)}. \quad (18)$$

- *Rich Club Coefficient* (Φ): This quantifies the tendency for hubs (highly connected nodes) to connect with each other:

$$\Phi(\delta) = \frac{2|\mathcal{E}_{>\delta}|}{N_{>\delta}(N_{>\delta}-1)} \implies \Phi_{norm}(\delta) = \frac{\Phi(\delta)}{\Phi_{rand}(\delta)}, \quad (19)$$

where δ is degree threshold, and $|\mathcal{E}_{>\delta}|$ is the number of edges between nodes with degree greater than δ [5, 35].

4 Experiments

4.1 Experimental setup

4.1.1 Stratified split. To ensure the representation of development spectrum, we implemented a stratified three-way split (80/10/10). We based this on the clinical definitions of preterm and term ($GA < 37$ and $GA \geq 37$). This allowed us to ensure that each contained an equivalent distribution of the two main developmental classifications. This also ensured that the minority class (preterm) were appropriately distributed throughout all three splits.

4.1.2 Baseline models. In order to assess the efficacy of the proposed model, we compare with re-implementations of the models that were, to the best of our knowledge, closest to the aim. Therefore, we implement two alternatives, first a CVAE model reproduced from [21] and second a more traditional geometric generative model from [3]. Due to the nature of the model, [3] does not have a mechanism for modeling specific gestational ages, therefore this model is excluded from the gestational comparison metrics.

For a further comparison, we construct a baseline Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) based on the formulation from Ho et al. [11]. We implement both the standard DDPM and the DDIM variant [31], which allows for non-Markovian diffusion processes. For each, we run a vanilla model, with the same MLP backbone as our model, and a graph-aware model, where we use diffusion in place of flow-matching in our architecture, in order to assess the effect of the flow-matching itself.

In all comparisons, we use the same train/val/test indices, to ensure fair comparison. Moreover, we prompt each model to generate “datasets” with the same number of cases, and the same matched GA split as the test set. For a baseline, we compare the differences in distribution between the test and validation sets, which gives an indication of both how well the selected indices are representative but also of the natural expected variance within the real data.

4.1.3 Hold-one-out generation. To evaluate the model’s ability to interpolate across the GA spectrum, we perform a hold-one-out experiment. We select 4 target ages (30, 34, 38, 42 weeks) encompassing both preterm and term classes. For each target age, we excluded all training samples within a ± 0.5 week window, to ensure the model generates synthetic connectomes for ages not seen during training. This zero-shot evaluation tests the CFM framework’s capacity to learn the underlying process of brain development rather than simply memorizing training cases.

4.1.4 Ablations. We run ablation studies in order to observe the effect of each component on the resulting networks. The three ablations are: 1. Without hypergraph layer; 2. Without multihop transformer; 3. Without hypergraph or multihop. The results are displayed in Table 4. In addition, we compare the test set with the validation set (Table 5), in order to ensure representativeness of the sample beyond age.

5 Results

5.1 Continuous gestational age modeling

We can demonstrate the learning pattern of the Conditional Flow Matching by decomposing the learned flow trajectories between the noise and real brain data. This can be demonstrated through

Figure 2: Plot showing a decomposition of how the conditioning affects the flow. Yellow points indicate the end points for preterm infants, while blue indicate end points for term infants. Both cases start from the same Gaussian noise distribution.

PCA analysis. We can show the effect of conditioning by starting from identical Gaussian, and then projecting the paths to the data from each age condition. We demonstrate here with high and low GA values which is demonstrated in Figure 2.

To visualize the developmental trajectories learned by the model, we generated connectomes across the gestational-age spectrum using age conditions corresponding to the real dataset. Figure 3 compares the real and generated connectomes at ages spanning preterm and term development. The residuals plots demonstrate that the model preserves age-dependent structural patterns.

5.2 Zero-shot age interpolation

To assess whether the model learns a continuous developmental trajectory rather than memorizing age-specific examples, we perform a hold-one-out age interpolation experiment. Table 1 demonstrates results for the hold-one-out comparing to diffusion baseline and CVAE. Across all held-out ages, our flow-matching model consistently outperforms the diffusion baseline and achieves competitive performance compared to the CVAE. The flow-matching model achieves the lowest errors for clustering and efficiency at three of the four ages, and consistently maintains low spectral Wasserstein distances. This indicates that the model captures age-dependent changes in connectivity, and supports the ability of the model to interpolate across the GA spectrum.

5.3 Generative Fidelity

5.3.1 Global performance. Results from Table 2 show that our full model achieves the best scores overall for global performance metrics. From this table we can see that our full model outperforms all comparison models on all metrics, with the exception of W_{val} where we are second to the CVAE. This suggests that while the CVAE is able to reproduce appropriate edge strengths globally, it does so at the expense of structural organization. Figure 3 demonstrates that the Flow Matching layer is able to appropriately generate a range

Figure 3: Developmental trajectories across GA spectrum. The figure displays ground truth (top), synthetic connectomes (middle) and comparison of residual error (bottom).

of different ages across GA. In the residual heatmaps, areas that are near-white represent near-perfect reconstruction, while faint red or blue spots highlight where the model either slightly overestimates or underestimates connection strength. This therefore, demonstrates a high similarity between the age-matched cases.

5.3.2 Topological fidelity. From Table 3, we demonstrate that our approach can identify and reproduce complex network features that are characteristics of the real brain data. Our full model achieves the lowest error for C , indicating that the generative model reproduces the density and efficiency in line with real data. Moreover, the ω results demonstrate competitive “small-world” connectivity, which is a key feature of human brain connectomes [13] as it illustrates the balance between local clustering and global integration. Similarly, “rich club” results are also important, as they have been implicated as critical features of neurodevelopment, and particular markers in preterm birth [2, 16].

5.4 Architectural analysis

5.4.1 Ablations. In Table 4 we evaluate the impact of each component of the model on validation performance. From this we see that the full model performs the best, followed by the model with no multihop transformer. This suggests the dynamic hypergraph layer is the most impactful component, which can be improved by including the transformer layer.

This is further supported by the Tables 2 and 3, which demonstrates that on both global and local scales, the removal of the hypergraph leads to collapse in fidelity. This reinforces the biological hypothesis that higher-order relationships are the key to gestational development of the brain structural connectome. While the model with no multihop transformer generally performs well across metrics, there is an increased error particularly for the small-worldness, which suggests that the transformer still provides insight into how local clusters become globally integrated.

Table 1: Zero-Shot Continuous Age Interpolation (Hold-One-Out). Ages 30, 34, 38, 42 weeks generated by flow-matching, graph-aware diffusion, standard diffusion and CVAE baselines.

Age	Model	W_{val}	W_{spec}	C MAE	ϵ MAE
30	Flow (Ours)	0.051	0.979	0.010	0.009
	CVAE	0.051	1.502	0.014	0.015
	GA-DDIM	0.184	2.499	0.182	0.074
	DDPM	12.062	27.536	0.426	0.606
34	Flow (Ours)	0.120	0.635	0.022	0.026
	CVAE	0.018	0.500	0.007	0.006
	GA-DDIM	0.240	2.773	0.059	0.168
	DDPM	12.470	24.840	0.448	0.607
38	Flow (Ours)	0.025	0.285	0.010	0.001
	CVAE	0.019	0.417	0.030	0.020
	GA-DDIM	0.187	1.028	0.030	0.177
	DDPM	12.539	24.981	0.459	0.613
42	Flow (Ours)	0.034	0.560	0.017	0.002
	CVAE	0.019	0.569	0.002	0.006
	GA-DDIM	0.506	11.201	0.162	0.110
	DDPM	12.512	24.919	0.455	0.608

Table 2: Global Performance. N.B. W_{spec} and W_{val} represent distributional distances and are null for the ground truth. Ground truth row represents raw metric means; other rows represent MAE. \pm denotes the standard deviation of the error across the $n = 53$ unseen test set samples.

Model	ϵ	W_{spec}	W_{val}
Ground Truth	0.388	—	—
Flow (Ours)	0.012 \pm 0.008	0.998 \pm 0.624	0.041 \pm 0.019
No Hypergraph	0.189 \pm 0.011	1.157 \pm 0.526	0.149 \pm 0.015
No Multihop	0.026 \pm 0.012	0.812 \pm 0.514	0.067 \pm 0.015
Baseline MLP	0.188 \pm 0.016	1.295 \pm 0.673	0.143 \pm 0.020
Geometric [3]	0.028 \pm 0.024	3.214 \pm 0.852	0.135 \pm 0.020
CVAE [21]	0.015 \pm 0.011	0.903 \pm 0.754	0.037 \pm 0.023
DDPM	0.360 \pm 0.012	190.171 \pm 3.142	15.721 \pm 0.421
GA-DDPM	0.099 \pm 0.022	13.142 \pm 8.103	0.588 \pm 0.337
DDIM	0.359 \pm 0.012	134.141 \pm 2.877	10.858 \pm 0.304
GA-DDIM	0.085 \pm 0.053	4.275 \pm 3.399	0.221 \pm 0.148

5.4.2 *Biological meaning in latent hyperedges.* To assess the biological relevance of the learned hyperedges, we extracted the final hyperedge membership matrix H and examined the regions with the largest memberships in each hyperedge. Several hyperedges corresponded to established large-scale brain systems [40]. For example, Hyperedge 17 contained predominantly occipital and superior parietal regions, including the cuneus and superior/middle occipital gyri, resembling the occipito-parietal dorsal visual pathway [17]. Hyperedge 20 linked superior and inferior parietal, supplementary motor, paracentral, and dorsolateral frontal regions, consistent with

Table 3: Topological Fidelity. N.B. Ground truth row represents raw metric means; other rows represent MAE. \pm denotes the standard deviation of the error across the $n = 53$ unseen test set samples.

Model	C	ω	RC
Ground Truth	0.546	4.350	1.040 \pm 0.172
Flow (Ours)	0.020 \pm 0.016	0.492 \pm 1.790	0.191 \pm 0.158
No Hypergraph	0.290 \pm 0.024	3.117 \pm 1.815	0.217 \pm 0.153
No Multihop	0.038 \pm 0.026	0.580 \pm 1.827	0.171 \pm 0.134
Baseline MLP	0.288 \pm 0.027	3.108 \pm 1.832	0.221 \pm 0.168
Geometric [3]	0.030 \pm 0.024	5.918 \pm 2.619	0.493 \pm 0.270
CVAE [21]	0.025 \pm 0.017	0.445 \pm 1.781	0.197 \pm 0.137
DDPM	0.050 \pm 0.021	3.559 \pm 1.818	0.169 \pm 0.118
GA-DDPM	0.131 \pm 0.029	1.250 \pm 1.814	0.142 \pm 0.115
DDIM	0.052 \pm 0.022	3.560 \pm 1.817	0.155 \pm 0.123
GA-DDIM	0.129 \pm 0.118	2.051 \pm 5.536	0.150 \pm 0.121

Table 4: Ablation study of our model testing the impact of different architectural components. The table highlights accuracy on validation loss.

Model Name	Architecture		Best Val. Loss
	Transformer	Hypergraph	
Full	✓	✓	0.148
Multihop	✓	×	0.432
Hypergraph	×	✓	0.194
Baseline MLP	×	×	0.434

Table 5: Consistency between validation and test set. This demonstrates that while both splits are small ($n = 53$), they include similar distributions for each graph network feature.

Metric	Variance (p -value)	Mean (p -value)
Clustering Coefficient (C)	0.178	0.175
Global Efficiency (ϵ)	0.165	0.355
Characteristic Path Length (L)	0.174	0.432
Small-Worldness (ω)	0.956	0.495

Note: High p -values indicate no significant distributional shift.

a frontoparietal attention and visuomotor control network overlapping the dorsal attention system [40]. These findings suggest that the model captures biologically meaningful higher-order connectivity motifs from structural connectivity alone (Appendix B).

Table 6: Comparison of classification for preterm and term across real and synthetic datasets.

Data	Class	Precision	Recall	F1	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC
Real	Preterm	0.76 ± 0.18	0.53 ± 0.17	0.61 ± 0.16	—	—
	Term	0.89 ± 0.05	0.96 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.03	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.75 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.08
Ours (Flow)	Preterm	0.37 ± 0.22	0.19 ± 0.12	0.23 ± 0.13	—	—
	Term	0.81 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.05	0.86 ± 0.04	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.55 ± 0.06	0.54 ± 0.07
CVAE	Preterm	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	—	—
	Term	0.79 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.04	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.49 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.01

6 Use case: Binary classification

In order to test usability of the generated data, we implement a fuzzy logistic regression (LR) classifier based on prior work [4] which found that due to individual differences in biology, and in estimating GA, it can be difficult to define exactly which infants are premature [4, 8, 14, 15, 23] when using a hard decision boundary ($GA < 37$). Therefore, we apply a continuous fuzzy logic function to the continuous GA to derive sample weights, in order to relax the penalties around the decision boundary. To assess the generalizability of the model, and account for the limited size of the test set, we use a bootstrapping strategy, reporting metrics across 100 iterations. We assess discriminative fidelity by training on the real ground truth data, and then evaluating strictly on the synthetic samples matching the real age distribution in the test set. The results in Table 6 demonstrate that the real test set can be classified with high precision and recall between classes. When classifying the CVAE dataset, the model suffered mode collapse, failing to identify any preterm cases (preterm F1 of 0.00 ± 0.00) and low balanced accuracy and ROC-AUC. In contrast, our Flow-Matching model, successfully preserved minority class representation, achieving preterm F1 of 0.23 ± 0.13 and overall balanced accuracy of 0.55 ± 0.06 . While this is a reduction compared to the real data, it demonstrates a large improvement over the CVAE model, as it demonstrates the models ability to preserve and reproduce connectivity patterns specific to preterm cases.

In order to assess the real-world clinical utility of our model [24, 34], we augment the real dataset with synthetic data generated through our Flow-Matching model. We conduct a ratio-sweep, observing the impact of training with varying synthetic-to-real ratio, on the LR ability to classify the real test set. Across augmentation levels, Table A (Appendix) demonstrates the highest mean preterm F1 score and ROC-AUC at 0.5 synthetic-to-real ratio, while larger ratios did not produce further improvements in these values. Further, we note that the synthetic data makes the classifier more sensitive to preterm infants by demonstrating a high recall even at low ratios. However, this comes at the expense of precision, where we see a higher rate of false positives.

7 Future work and conclusion

While our model produces state-of-the-art generations, the recall between preterm and term classes is still not ideal. Future work

should focus on further mitigating the bias towards the majority class, in order to fully take advantage of the model’s ability to generate networks across the full gestational range. While the model is demonstrating ability to reproduce preterm brain differences, in order to use the model for clinical outcome prediction, future work should incorporate longitudinal data.

In this paper, we assessed the sufficiency and plausibility of generating synthetic brain networks for infants based on their time of birth (GA). Previous works have relied on static reconstructions of real data, or purely statistical generation methods, where GA cannot be modeled. In our method, we introduced a model which is capable of generating brain connectivity as a continuous trajectory. This provides a platform for interpolating between GAs where there is data sparsity. Moreover, our model is able to implicitly learn higher-order structure as a function of gestational development. We test the appropriateness of our data, through a combination of biologically informed losses, statistical metrics, and neurobiological graph-based metrics. In addition, we consider these in terms of trajectories. Our results demonstrate that the architecture can successfully learn and reproduce the brain’s capacity for self-organization on local and global levels. Ultimately we demonstrate how the complex motifs of the human brain connectome can be captured through Conditional Flow Matching and learned higher-order structural priors. This offers a framework for modeling and exploring the differences at continuous stages of gestational development.

8 Limitations and Ethical Considerations

When working with the human data, it is important to ensure that individual participants cannot be reidentified. We have no information about the specific participants identities, and all infants are assigned index identifiers purely for the case of consistency in training. In the preparation of this manuscript, we utilized generative AI tools to enhance the research writing quality, adhering to the principles of responsible and transparent use. All AI-generated suggestions for text and structure were reviewed, edited, and approved by the human authors to ensure they reflect our research contributions and scientific voice. The core ideas, experimental methodology, analysis, and conclusions presented in this paper are entirely the work of the human authors.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) Grant no. [2753824] through a DTP Studentship for the University of Surrey awarded to K. Birch. Data were provided by the developing Human Connectome Project, KCL-Imperial-Oxford Consortium funded by the European Research Council under the European Union Seventh Framework Programme (FP/2007-2013) / ERC Grant Agreement no. [319456]. We are grateful to the families who generously supported this trial.

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A Detailed Classification Results

Table 7: Classification performance for preterm and term across augmentation ratio datasets. Ratio of synthetic to real training data. Results are presented as mean (standard deviation) across 100 bootstrapped iterations of the holdout test set.

Ratio	Class	Prec.	Recall	F1	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC
0.00	Preterm	0.76 ± 0.18	0.53 ± 0.17	0.61 ± 0.16	—	—
	Term	0.89 ± 0.05	0.96 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.03	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.75 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.08
0.25	Preterm	0.51 ± 0.12	0.72 ± 0.14	0.58 ± 0.11	—	—
	Term	0.92 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.06	0.87 ± 0.04	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.77 ± 0.07	0.78 ± 0.09
0.50	Preterm	0.55 ± 0.12	0.74 ± 0.14	0.62 ± 0.11	—	—
	Term	0.92 ± 0.05	0.83 ± 0.06	0.87 ± 0.04	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.79 ± 0.07	0.79 ± 0.09
1.00	Preterm	0.52 ± 0.14	0.73 ± 0.14	0.59 ± 0.12	—	—
	Term	0.93 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.06	0.88 ± 0.04	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.78 ± 0.08	0.78 ± 0.09
2.00	Preterm	0.55 ± 0.13	0.75 ± 0.14	0.62 ± 0.12	—	—
	Term	0.92 ± 0.05	0.83 ± 0.06	0.88 ± 0.05	—	—
	Overall	—	—	—	0.79 ± 0.08	0.77 ± 0.09

B Biological hyperedges

Table 8: Top anatomical regions and their corresponding mean weights for a selection of learned latent hyperedges.

HE ID	Anatomical Region	Mean Weight
0	Rolandic operculum	1.00
	Inferior frontal gyrus, orbital part	1.00
	Superior frontal gyrus, orbital part	1.00
	Superior frontal gyrus, dorsolateral	1.00
	Precentral gyrus	1.00
2	Supramarginal gyrus	1.00
	Postcentral gyrus	1.00
	Superior temporal gyrus	1.00
	Middle temporal gyrus	1.00
4	Angular gyrus	0.99
	Middle occipital gyrus	0.98
	Superior occipital gyrus	0.98
	Inferior parietal, but supramarginal and angular gyri	0.98
	Cuneus	0.97
17	Superior parietal gyrus	1.00
	Supplementary motor area	1.00
	Paracentral lobule	1.00
	Superior frontal gyrus, dorsolateral	1.00
	Inferior parietal, but supramarginal and angular gyri	1.00
30	Temporal pole: middle temporal gyrus	1.00
	Inferior frontal gyrus, orbital part	1.00
	Inferior temporal gyrus	1.00
	Middle temporal gyrus	1.00
	Fusiform gyrus	1.00